

The Impact of deep learning framework, namely GAN on fashion Industry.

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Deep learning in recent years has certainly become the biggest trend in Machine Learning (ML). DL is growing through different technological areas, for example: Computer Vision or Natural Language processing. At the central level, DL is defined as a hierarchy of algorithms that has a great capacity for self-learning, for that the self-learning algorithm must have a set of quality data that contains a correct repetition of the activity instances that should be resolved via the algorithm. Therefore, the core technology of DL is that algorithms can learn the relationships of the answers to the question. To justify this, one strong example would be, a deep learning system that aims to identify items of clothing in pictures that will need to feed images that are labeled as such.

The ability to automatically transform raw unstructured data to meaningful features has made deep learning a game changer in problems related to the analysis of images, video, and text. While exploring the ability of DL on Fashion Industry, In ArXiv, the researchers from the University of California, San Diego, and Adobe have outlined a way for AI to not only learn a person's style but create computer-generated images of items that match that style and many more use cases are developed. The system was further improvised to varied level of output functionalities, this helps fashion industries to grow with technology and keep up with the trends and needs of their consumers.

The most used Deep learning framework to improve the technological perspective of Fashion Industry is Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), the underlining logic of GAN framework has made it the most suitable. There are many limitations currently when we talk about the technology perspective in Fashion industry, but GAN seems to aid all of them with its right use.

Fashion seems to be ready for an intrusion of artificial intelligence, however, in order not to neglect it, it is a field that has the incredible set of information on the client's interests, and there is a considerable amount of money at stake. Amazon, for example, is now sneaking out of artificial intelligence structures to give an edge in detecting style models, and has also worked a bit with GAN (see "Amazon has developed a stylist AI"). Alibaba, meanwhile, has just appeared FashionAI, an innovation that can prescribe things to customers based

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on what they have brought to the changing area. GAN will continue to make waves in the online mold.

2. Aim

To depict the utilization of GAN in the field of fashion industry.

Author biography

Dinesh Prasanna Arivalagan graduated from Brindavan College of Engineering in Information Science under Visvesvaraya Technological University, Further pursued M.Sc[Engg] under Coventry UK. Currently pursuing Ph.D under the specialization of Computer Vision and Deep Learning under REVA University, India. Have published and guided graduate and post graduate students in various inter disciplinary domains of engineering. Have authored research topics in various international journals and chapters. The core interest areas are blockchain, artificial intelligence, augmented reality, robotics, embedded systems and cyber security. He started his career in 2012 as the founder of Prosquare Infotech, Bangalore. Currently working as a senior researcher in the field of Computer Vision and Deep Learning in Gimme360, Canada.